

Stimulating the Senses: How Online Culture and Heritage Events Support Wellbeing for People Living with Dementia

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

People living with dementia (PWD) often face barriers that limit their access to cultural and social activities, especially when travel or in person attendance is difficult. This was highlighted during the Covid-19 pandemic, where online cultural and heritage events emerged as an important way to reduce isolation and support well-being. This research explored how to design online events that are enjoyable, inclusive and genuinely supportive for PWD and their carers. The research aimed to identify what makes online cultural events work well, understand participants' experiences and challenges and develop a framework to guide culture and heritage organisations in creating engaging and accessible online programming.

Research Findings

Online events for PWD provide an opportunity for social interaction and stimulation for individuals. While many people prefer physical events, there is clear evidence that online events can be impactful. In this paper, we co-created a new framework based on the "Six Senses" (continuity, significance, security, belonging, achievement and purpose) which can be utilised to create meaningful online events for PWD. Participants valued sessions that were friendly, interactive and easy to follow. Events worked best when they combined social conversation, short presentations and simple hands-on activities.

Policy Implications

Policymakers should recognise online cultural programming as a meaningful form of social support for PWD. Public bodies and cultural institutions should ensure dementia-inclusive digital access by simplifying booking systems, reducing technical barriers and investing in accessible digital platforms. National dementia strategies can benefit from integrating online cultural participation as part of social prescribing, community engagement and human rights-based care. Sustained funding is needed to support hybrid cultural programmes that reach people in rural areas, people with mobility challenges and those who cannot attend in person. Clear guidance can help organisations adopt dementia-informed design.

Industry Recommendations

Cultural, heritage and arts organisations should design online events that are welcoming, simple to join and centred on familiar, enjoyable experiences. Sessions should follow a clear structure: friendly social chat, a short visual presentation and an easy, hands-on activity. Event hosts should provide digital help in advance, use accessible platforms (e.g., Zoom), send materials beforehand where possible and keep content short and engaging. Marketing must clearly state that events are for people affected by dementia to avoid unintentionally excluding the target audience. By adopting these practices, organisations can create meaningful online cultural experiences that build community and support well-being.

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Further Reading:

Kerr, G.W., Stewart, H., Smith, S.
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and revive: co-producing impactful
and accessible online culture and
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with dementia, *International
Journal of Event and Festival
Management*, 16(3), 402–425.
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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Audio-visual / Creative

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

SDG 3: Good Health & Wellbeing

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